

Mitral Valve Anatomy Analysis Using Multimodal Imaging Data: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Mitral Valve Anatomy Analysis Using Multimodal Imaging Data

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

MVAA

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Mitral valve (MV) disease is one of the most prevalent cardiovascular disorders and requires accurate assessment of annular geometry, leaflet morphology, and subvalvular structures for diagnosis, surgical planning, and transcatheter intervention. In current clinical workflows, multiple imaging modalities are used for complementary purposes. Three-dimensional transesophageal echocardiography (3D TEE) serves as the intraoperative reference for evaluating leaflet motion and valve function, but accurate segmentation of thin, deformable leaflets remains difficult due to acoustic noise and shadowing. Cardiac CT provides clearer visualization of annular landmarks and spatial geometry for pre-procedural planning, yet lacks real-time capability. Surgical videos offer direct visualization of leaflet motion and device interaction but require robust tracking and interpretation. Although these modalities are routinely used together in practice, no unified automated pipeline currently exists to provide consistent mitral valve measurements across the full clinical workflow.

Our team has extensive experience in organizing large-scale medical image analysis benchmarks at MICCAI, including eight prior international challenges across cardiac MR, CT, and ultrasound imaging. These efforts have established a mature multi-center data collaboration and evaluation infrastructure and have supported the development of clinically meaningful segmentation, landmark detection, and measurement algorithms. This foundation enables the construction of a reliable multimodal benchmark for mitral valve analysis.

Despite recent technical advances, existing methods for MV analysis remain fragmented and rarely align with real clinical decision-making. Most current approaches are limited to a single imaging modality or a single subtask, such as annulus segmentation or leaflet detection, and therefore cannot provide the integrated anatomical measurements required for intervention planning. As a result, clinicians still rely heavily on manual measurements, which are time-consuming and subject to inter-operator variability. Furthermore, models trained

on one modality often generalize poorly to others due to differences in imaging conditions and acquisition protocols, limiting their practical deployment.

To address these gaps, the proposed benchmark establishes a clinically oriented multimodal framework for automated mitral valve anatomy analysis across CT, 3D TEE, and surgical video data. The three tasks are designed to reflect real clinical usage rather than isolated technical objectives. CT-based analysis provides accurate annular geometry for pre-procedural sizing and device selection; 3D TEE segmentation supports intraoperative assessment of leaflet morphology and valve function; and surgical video analysis enables confirmation of leaflet motion and device-tissue interaction during intervention. Together, these tasks aim to support consistent anatomical understanding across pre-operative planning, intra-operative guidance, and post-operative evaluation.

Importantly, the benchmark encourages unified and cross-task modeling strategies. Anatomical priors derived from CT can support TEE-based leaflet analysis, while motion cues from surgical videos provide temporal validation of structural consistency. Such cross-modal integration promotes the development of coherent and generalizable models that better reflect real clinical workflows.

The final outputs of the challenge are clinically interpretable measurements—including commissural width, anteroposterior diameter, saddle height, and leaflet angles—which directly inform routine decision-making in mitral valve repair, transcatheter edge-to-edge repair (TEER), and annuloplasty. By linking algorithm performance to these clinically meaningful metrics, the proposed benchmark aims to improve measurement reproducibility, reduce operator dependence, and support more consistent intervention planning and outcome assessment. Ultimately, this challenge will provide a standardized and clinically grounded evaluation platform to accelerate the translation of multimodal AI methods into real-world cardiac care.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Mitral Valve; Echocardiography; Computed Tomography; Surgical Video; Multimodal Imaging; Segmentation; Landmark Detection; Semi-supervised learning; Foundational Model

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

This challenge is novel in three key aspects.

We introduce a unique multimodal dataset that integrates 3D echocardiography, cardiac CT, and intraoperative surgical videos, enabling the community to explore cross-modal learning and information fusion for structural heart disease, which has been rarely addressed in existing benchmarks. Beyond providing modality-specific datasets, this design supports unified anatomical modeling and encourages the exploration of modality-agnostic representations across pre-operative, intra-operative, and peri-operative imaging scenarios.

Unlike conventional challenges focusing on isolated image analysis tasks, this challenge is surgically driven, aiming to support valve sizing and optimal placement through combined segmentation and anatomical landmark localization, directly reflecting clinical decision-making requirements in valve interventions. The challenge further emphasizes cross-task scientific integration: rather than treating segmentation, landmark detection, and multimodal analysis as independent objectives, the design encourages shared anatomical priors, geometry-consistent modeling, and multi-stage pipelines that jointly optimize performance across modalities and tasks. This unified framework enables participants to develop coherent representations of mitral valve anatomy that remain consistent across imaging modalities and clinical stages.

The challenge is closely aligned with real-world clinical workflows, with data collected from routine clinical practice and tasks designed around actual surgical needs, thereby strongly promoting clinical relevance, translational impact, and downstream adoption of the developed methods. By fostering cross-modal and cross-task learning opportunities within a clinically grounded benchmarking framework, the challenge supports the development of next-generation generalizable and multimodal foundation models for structural heart analysis.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The proposed challenge focuses on automatic, multi-class anatomical segmentation and reconstruction of the mitral valve (MV) from clinically acquired cardiac imaging data, with a primary focus on the mitral annulus and anterior/posterior leaflets. Rather than treating each task as an isolated technical problem, the benchmark is designed to reflect how mitral valve assessment is performed in real clinical workflows across multiple imaging modalities. The three tasks therefore work together to support consistent anatomical understanding across pre-procedural planning, intra-operative guidance, and post-operative follow-up.

To improve scientific coherence and practical relevance, the tasks are structured to encourage cross-task and multimodal learning. For example, annular geometry and landmark information derived from cardiac CT can provide reliable structural priors for leaflet segmentation in 3D transesophageal echocardiography (TEE), while surgical videos offer direct visualization of leaflet motion and device-tissue interaction that helps validate anatomical consistency. This complementary use of structural and temporal information supports the development of unified models capable of producing coherent mitral valve representations across imaging stages and clinical settings.

Pre-procedural planning for mitral valve interventions.

Automated MV segmentation and reconstruction enable quantitative assessment of key anatomical measurements—such as commissural width, anteroposterior diameter, and saddle height—which directly inform device sizing, repair strategy selection, and procedural planning for mitral valve repair, transcatheter edge-to-edge repair (TEER), annuloplasty, and minimally invasive surgery. Providing these measurements in a standardized and reproducible manner can improve consistency in treatment planning across institutions and operators.

Intra-operative and intraprocedural guidance.

During 3D TEE-guided procedures, rapid and reliable delineation of MV structures can provide real-time

anatomical context, helping clinicians confirm leaflet grasping, annular alignment, and device positioning. This reduces reliance on manual interpretation and supports safer and more consistent interventions. Surgical video analysis further complements imaging-based assessment by enabling verification of leaflet motion and structural continuity.

Post-operative assessment and follow-up.

Standardized anatomical measurements derived from automated analysis support objective comparison across time points, allowing clinicians to evaluate procedural outcomes, monitor valve remodeling, and assess device positioning during follow-up. By linking automated outputs directly to clinically interpretable measurements used in routine care, the proposed framework aims to reduce measurement variability and improve decision consistency throughout the treatment pathway.

Overall, the challenge emphasizes clinically interpretable outputs and cross-modal consistency rather than isolated algorithmic performance. By aligning automated measurements with routine clinical decision-making, the benchmark aims to support the development of practical and generalizable tools for mitral valve assessment across the full patient care workflow.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

The 1st MICCAI Workshop on Medical World Models

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

Although up to 30 teams may participate, not all presentations will be delivered on-site. Most presentations will be conducted online (e.g., virtual or pre-recorded). From these, no more than three representative top teams will be invited for on-site presentations during the MICCAI workshop, together with the challenge overview and discussion. The final on-site program will fit within an approximately two-hour schedule and is now clearly described.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

Our estimate is grounded in participation statistics from our previous, closely related international challenges and workshops in the medical ultrasound and MICCAI communities. Specifically, the PSFHS Challenge at MICCAI 2023 attracted 187 registered participants, while the IUGC Challenge at MICCAI 2024 received 125 team registrations from 18 countries, demonstrating strong and sustained global engagement. More recently, the IUGC Challenge at MICCAI 2025, co-organized with ASMUS 2025 (The 6th International Workshop on Advances in Simplifying Medical UltraSound), recorded 213 participants. Based on this consistent participation trend across three consecutive

years, we conservatively anticipate more than 100 participating teams in the proposed challenge.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

1. We will coordinate post-conference proceedings associated with the challenge, enabling participating teams to publish detailed descriptions of their methods in the Springer Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS) volumes linked to the 1st MICCAI Workshop on Medical World Models.
2. Outstanding and high-impact contributions will be invited to submit extended manuscripts to the IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering (TBME) Special Issue entitled "Digital Twins, Simulation-Based AI and Medical World Models." This pathway provides an opportunity for selected teams to present deeper methodological insights, extended validation, and translational perspectives beyond the scope of proceedings papers.
3. We will coordinate journal-level challenge summary manuscripts that comprehensively report and analyze the outcomes of the challenge. These papers will synthesize results across all participating methods, conduct comparative and meta-analyses, and highlight key findings, trends, and open challenges. Such summary reports are intended to serve as authoritative references for the community, informing future research directions and benchmarking practices.

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

Yes

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team ([miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de](mailto:micca-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de)) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

For the online components of the challenge, CodaLab will be used as the official platform for submission, evaluation, and ranking. Participants will develop and train their algorithms using their own computing infrastructure, ensuring full flexibility in model design and optimization. During the testing phase, submissions

will be evaluated on CodaLab against a hidden test set using standardized evaluation scripts, metrics, and execution settings, providing a transparent, reproducible, and fair benchmarking environment independent of local hardware differences.

TASK 1: Mitral Valve Segmentation and Landmark Localization in CT scans

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Accurate assessment of the mitral valve (MV) anatomy is critical for the diagnosis, planning, and guidance of both surgical and transcatheter mitral valve interventions. Cardiac computed tomography (CT) has become an essential imaging modality for preoperative evaluation due to its high spatial resolution and comprehensive visualization of cardiac structures. However, precise segmentation of the mitral valve apparatus and reliable localization of clinically meaningful anatomical landmarks remain challenging, owing to complex valve geometry, inter-patient anatomical variability, and limited availability of high-quality annotated datasets.

This challenge aims to establish a standardized benchmark for mitral valve segmentation and landmark localization in cardiac CT scans, fostering the development and fair comparison of robust, automated algorithms. From a biomedical perspective, the challenge focuses on anatomically and clinically relevant MV components and landmarks that are directly associated with valve sizing, spatial orientation, and procedural planning. From a technical perspective, it promotes advanced image analysis methods capable of handling fine-grained structures, ambiguous boundaries, and anatomical variability within volumetric CT data.

By providing a curated dataset, unified evaluation protocols, and clinically motivated tasks, this challenge seeks to bridge the gap between algorithmic innovation and real-world clinical needs. The envisioned impact is to accelerate the development of reliable AI tools for mitral valve analysis, enhance reproducibility and comparability across methods, and ultimately support more precise, personalized, and clinically translatable decision-making in mitral valve interventions.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Mitral Valve; Computed Tomography; Segmentation; Landmark Detection; Semi-supervised learning; Foundational Model

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Organizers:

1. Mohamed Hammad (Prince Sultan University)
2. Jieyun Bai (The University of Auckland)
3. Jichao Zhao (The University of Auckland)
4. Karim Lekadir (University of Barcelona)
5. Jun Ma (University of Toronto)

6. Kuanquan Wang (Harbin Institute of Technology)

7. Shuo Li (Case Western Reserve University)

Advisors:

1. Mohammad Yaqub (Mohamed bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence)

2. Islem Rekik (Imperial College London)

3. Weidong Cai (University of Sydney)

Contributors:

1. Jie Gan (University of Sydney)

2. Xiaoshen Zhang (The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University)

3. Hua Lu (The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University)

4. Yufei Zhan (The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Mohamed Hammad (mhammad@psu.edu.sa)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes, clinicians are an integral part of the organizing team and play a central role in ensuring the clinical relevance, annotation quality, and overall validity of the challenge. The clinical experts involved include Xiaoshen Zhang, Hua Lu, and Yufei Zhan (The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University), as well as Xiaowei Xu (Guangdong Provincial People's Hospital). Their primary responsibilities include:

1. Providing real-world clinical data acquired under routine diagnostic conditions across multiple institutions and patient populations;
2. Performing and supervising expert annotations, including landmark identification and segmentation mask labeling, in accordance with standardized clinical protocols;
3. Evaluating annotation quality and inter-rater consistency to ensure that the reference labels accurately reflect true clinical variability and meet established diagnostic standards.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

The 1st MICCAI Workshop on Medical World Models in MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

<https://www.codabench.org/>

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

The official website is not yet publicly available at this stage. For reference, the previous IUGC 2025 was hosted on the CodaBench platform at: <https://www.codabench.org/competitions/7108/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Participants are required to use all unlabeled data to develop semi-supervised methods

We expect the solution to process one case within 10 seconds on a 12 GB GPU.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Participants were allowed to use only publicly available external datasets and publicly released pre-trained models.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

1. Certificates and cash awards for the top teams, the team with the most innovative method, and the teams with the careful method description.

2. The top 10 teams will be invited to give oral presentations at the MICCAI 2026 event and will be encouraged to submit extended versions of their methods to a related IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering (TBME) Special Issue.

3. Co-author of the challenge compendium paper, which will be submitted to a top journal (Media/TMI).

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The top 10 performing methods will be publicly announced by the organizers. The announcement will include the team names and overall ranking based on the official evaluation metrics defined for the challenge.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

1. Authorship Qualification: Members of top-10 teams who have made significant contributions to the conceptualization, design, execution, or interpretation of the research presented are qualified as authors.

2. Independent Publications: Participating teams are allowed to publish their results separately. However, this should be done in a manner that respects the collective efforts of the challenge.

3. Embargo Period: An embargo period allows the challenge organizers to publish a comprehensive challenge paper first. During this period, individual teams are encouraged to refrain from publishing their complete findings independently.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker container

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participating teams are allowed to validate their methods using the validation set provided by the organizers. Each submission will receive a validation score, which serves solely as a sanity check to verify that the submission is complete and correctly formatted. This validation score is not used for algorithm ranking, comparative evaluation, or determination of final challenge results.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)

- the release date(s) of the results

Training data release: 15/04/2026

Validation data release: 01/06/2026

Evaluation: 01/07/2026

Submission deadline: 01/08/2026

Winner and invitation speakers: 01/09/2026

Announcement of results at MICCAI 2026: (subject to change depending on the MICCAI 2026 deadlines)

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

All data is anonymized. Ethics approval by the Medical Ethics Committee (No. KY-N-2022-048-01).

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation software developed by the organizers will be publicly available to all participants. The code used for submission evaluation and ranking generation will be hosted in an open repository (e.g., GitHub), accompanied by comprehensive documentation, usage instructions, and platform requirements. A direct repository link will be provided on the challenge website, allowing participants to download, review, and locally run the evaluation pipeline to validate their submissions before final testing.

To facilitate fair comparison and help participants calibrate model development, an official baseline model will also be released. This will include a reference implementation, a pre-trained foundation-model checkpoint, and

detailed instructions for fine-tuning and inference on the challenge dataset. Baseline performance scores will be provided as a transparent reference for benchmarking and result interpretation.

This open-access evaluation framework, together with the baseline-supported design, ensures transparency, reproducibility, and fairness throughout the challenge while enabling meaningful and consistent comparison across all participating methods.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Algorithm code release and corresponding conference paper submission will be prerequisites for award eligibility and further use of the data. To this end, GitHub repository URL containing the source code for their implemented method and conference paper following the guidelines will need to be provided.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The organizers declare no conflicts of interest.

During the challenge, only the organizers have access to the test dataset and its labels. Participating teams have no access to the test annotations. All test labels will be publicly released six months after the conclusion of the challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

CAD, Intervention planning, Research, Surgery, Training, Treatment planning, Intervention follow up, Longitudinal study

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Localization, Segmentation, Reconstruction

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort consists of adult patients with severe mitral valve stenosis or regurgitation. In the final biomedical application, data would be acquired from real clinical patients undergoing routine cardiac imaging and evaluation, where accurate assessment of mitral valve anatomy and function is required to support clinical decision-making and treatment planning.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort consists of mitral valve data acquired from adult patients with severe mitral valve stenosis or regurgitation.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Computed tomography (CT)

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The provided data include the original CT images, the corresponding mitral valve segmentation masks, and key point coordinates associated with the mitral valve for measurement and localization purposes.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No patient information is shared except for the labels. To ensure clinical relevance and address the gap between technical performance and practical utility, the challenge will include clinically measured anatomical parameters as part of the official evaluation framework. In addition to segmentation and landmark accuracy, reference measurements obtained from routine clinical assessment will be provided for key mitral valve metrics, including commissural width, anteroposterior (AP) diameter, and saddle height.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The image data are acquired from the cardiac region, specifically focusing on the mitral valve and adjacent cardiac structures, as visualized in cardiac CT images. Note: In this challenge, 40 cases have paired CT and surgical video data.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Mitral valve segmentation and landmark detection

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Complexity, Hardware requirements, Runtime, Sensitivity, Specificity

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Siemens Healthineers, GE Healthcare, Philips Healthcare, and Canon Medical Systems.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The size of the images is $512 \times 512 \times (275-571)$, and the typical voxel size is $0.25 \times 0.25 \times 0.5 \text{mm}^3$.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

ImageCAS dataset used in the MICCAI 2019 and our private dataset from Guangdong Provincial People's Hospital, The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University, and Dongguan Eastern Central Hospital. In this challenge, we annotate this dataset and provide pixel-level labels.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

The annotations were performed by three experienced radiologists with over 6-10 years of experience, and the time for labeling each image is 0.5-1.5 hours.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A "case" refers to the entire set of data associated with an individual patient's CT scan of the heart.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The dataset comprises a total of 1,167 high-resolution 3D cardiac CT scans, including 127 volumes with pixel-level annotations and 1,040 unlabeled scans in the training dataset. The labeled dataset is split into 27 training cases, 30 validation cases, and 70 test cases. All weakly labeled and unlabeled cases are used exclusively for training purposes.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

The quantity of annotated data, stratified by training, validation, and test sets in percentage, is as follows:

1. Training set: The training set consists of 1,067 images, among which 27 are fully annotated.
2. Validation set: The validation set consists of 30 images, all of which are fully annotated, accounting for 100%.
3. Test set: The test set consists of 70 images, all of which are fully annotated, accounting for 100%.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The proportion of annotated and unannotated data was intentionally designed to reflect a realistic semi-supervised learning scenario, where only a limited fraction of medical images can be exhaustively annotated

due to the high cost and expertise required. Therefore, approximately 10% of the data are fully annotated, while more than 90% remain unlabeled, which is appropriate for evaluating semi-supervised learning methods. Among the annotated data, 22% are used for training, 23% for validation, and 55% for testing. This split was chosen to balance the number of cases across validation and test sets while retaining sufficient labeled samples for supervised learning. All data splits include a mixture of healthy subjects and patients to ensure representative data distributions and robust evaluation.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The training, validation, and test cases are designed with several important characteristics to ensure clinical relevance and robust evaluation.

First, the class distribution reflects real-world clinical prevalence of different cardiac conditions rather than an artificially balanced distribution. This choice ensures that the developed methods are applicable to realistic clinical scenarios and can handle natural inter-patient variability.

Second, the dataset includes variability in imaging quality, arising from differences in CT scanners, acquisition protocols, and patient conditions. This diversity is intentionally preserved to simulate routine clinical practice and to encourage the development of robust and generalizable algorithms.

Third, the annotation strategy mirrors real-world constraints. While the training set contains pixel-level annotations, their availability is intentionally limited, consistent with typical clinical settings. Validation and test cases may have limited or no accessible annotations, challenging algorithms to generalize beyond fully supervised conditions.

Together, these characteristics ensure that the challenge closely reflects real clinical conditions and supports the development of methods suitable for practical deployment.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

We have provided a total of more than 140 newly collected, unpublished ultrasound images for the challenge. Notably, both the validation set and test set utilized in this challenge are composed entirely of unpublished data that has never been disclosed, shared, or reported in any prior research or public datasets.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Manual image annotation by three medical imaging experts.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The annotations are conducted according to the knowledge of annotators, using 3D slicer.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Pixel-level annotations were performed by three medically trained imaging experts following a two-stage annotation and quality-control process.

We employ a domain-specific manual annotation and quality-control pipeline involving nine professional annotators. For each anatomical or clinical domain, initial annotations are performed by a dedicated team consisting of an experienced sonographer and a trained annotator. All annotations are subsequently reviewed and adjudicated by senior clinical specialists.

To assess annotation reliability, inter-observer variability is evaluated on a randomly selected subset of 30 images, independently annotated by three annotators. We report (i) annotation variability using evaluation metrics, and (ii) agreement at the measurement level, including intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC) and absolute error distributions of derived clinical parameters. This procedure ensures the reliability and clinical validity of the reference annotations used for evaluation.

In the first stage, the images were independently annotated by two trained medical imaging experts each with more than three year of experience in interpreting cardiac CT images. These annotators produced detailed pixel-level segmentation masks based on established clinical criteria.

In the second stage, all annotations were reviewed and refined by a board-certified radiologist with over ten years of post-fellowship clinical experience, who provided final validation to ensure accuracy and consistency.

The same annotation and review protocol was applied consistently across the training, validation, and test datasets to ensure uniform annotation quality.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

For this challenge, we do not merge multiple annotations, instead, all annotations are published to participants.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Data are resampled to the same thick slicers and annotated on slice level.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

The main sources of annotation-related error include:

1. Inter-annotator variability: Differences in how annotators identify and delineate mitral valve structures, particularly in complex cases with subtle boundaries or low contrast. This variability may lead to differences in boundary placement and shape, typically within a small spatial range around the valve contours.
2. Intra-annotator variability: Variations in annotations produced by the same expert across different cases or at different times, arising from subjective interpretation or image quality differences. Such inconsistencies mainly affect fine-scale boundary details.
3. Annotation ambiguity: In some cases, the boundaries of the mitral valve are inherently ambiguous due to imaging limitations or pathological alterations, which can result in uncertain or partially overlapping annotations.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Technical Limitations: Errors introduced due to limitations of the annotation tools or image resolution.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), Hausdorff distance (HD), Mean Radial Error (MRE) and Inference Time

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) is used to quantify the spatial overlap between the predicted segmentation and the reference annotation, which is a standard and widely accepted metric for medical image segmentation. Accurate overlap is essential to ensure reliable delineation of the mitral valve anatomy.

Hausdorff Distance (HD) is included to evaluate boundary accuracy by measuring the maximum deviation between segmentation contours. This metric is particularly important for assessing clinically relevant boundary errors that may impact anatomical measurements and treatment planning.

ASD quantifies the average distance between corresponding surfaces and is therefore more sensitive to subtle boundary deviations that can significantly affect downstream anatomical measurements and surgical planning. Mean Radial Error (MRE) measures the localization error between predicted and reference anatomical landmarks. It directly reflects the precision of key point detection used for mitral valve measurement and positioning. Inference time is considered to assess computational efficiency, as timely results are critical for clinical workflows and real-time or near-real-time decision-making.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

Performance ranking is computed by aggregating results across all test cases and evaluation metrics into a single unified score. For each task, metric scores are first normalized to ensure comparability across different scales and optimization directions. The final task score is then calculated as a weighted combination of normalized metric scores, with the following weights: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) 30%, Hausdorff Distance (HD) 30%, Mean Radial Error (MRE) 30%, and Inference Time 10%. This weighting balances segmentation accuracy, boundary precision, landmark localization accuracy, and computational efficiency.

After computing task-level scores, the overall challenge ranking is obtained by aggregating the normalized scores from the three tasks with equal weights assigned to each task, ensuring consistency and fairness across modalities. By combining complementary metrics and normalized multi-task aggregation, this ranking strategy provides a holistic and clinically meaningful assessment of each algorithm's robustness, efficiency, and practical suitability for real-world deployment.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For submissions with missing results on one or more test cases, the missing values will be penalized by assigning a score equivalent to the worst performance observed for the corresponding metric among all valid submissions. This strategy ensures fair comparison and discourages incomplete submissions while maintaining a consistent ranking framework.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Performance ranking is computed by aggregating the results across all test cases and evaluation metrics into a single weighted score. The final ranking score is calculated as a weighted combination of normalized metric scores, with the following weights: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC): 30%, Hausdorff Distance (HD): 30%, Mean Radial Error (MRE): 30%, and Inference Time: 10%. DSC measures the spatial overlap between predicted segmentation and ground truth, ensuring reliable delineation of the mitral valve anatomy, which is critical in clinical applications. HD evaluates boundary accuracy, identifying discrepancies that could impact clinical decision-making, while MRE reflects the precision of key point detection for mitral valve measurement. Inference time assesses computational efficiency, which is important for real-time decision-making in clinical settings. This ranking scheme balances segmentation accuracy, boundary precision, landmark localization, and computational efficiency, providing a holistic assessment of each algorithm's clinical suitability and robustness, aligning with the challenge's objective of identifying reliable and practical solutions for real-world medical applications.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

The statistical approaches applied in the challenge analysis are structured as follows:

1. **Missing Data Handling:** Multiple imputation techniques will be adopted to address missing data, ensuring the robustness and reliability of the analysis despite incomplete dataset information.
2. **Ranking Variability Assessment:** Statistical metrics including standard deviation and confidence intervals will be calculated for each algorithm's performance across different evaluation indices, to quantify performance variability. Additionally, non-parametric tests (e.g., the Wilcoxon signed-rank test) will be employed to conduct pairwise comparisons of algorithm performance.
3. **Data Assumption Validation:** Prior to implementing any statistical methods, pre-validation tests will be performed on the dataset. This includes the Shapiro-Wilk test for assessing data normality and Levene's test for evaluating variance homogeneity, ensuring the dataset meets the prerequisite assumptions of the selected statistical approaches.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Performance estimate precision is evaluated using percentile bootstrap confidence intervals on the test set (95% CI, 1,000 resamples).

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Performance variability across test cases is evaluated using per-case metric distributions, reported via SD and IQR, supplemented with boxplots/violin plots and explicit outlier reporting.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap. The Bootstrap is a simple nonparametric method that relies on minimal assumptions.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Statistical significance of performance differences between algorithms is assessed using pairwise non-parametric hypothesis testing on per-case performance metrics computed on the test set. Specifically, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test is employed for paired comparisons, as all algorithms are evaluated on the same test cases and metric distributions may deviate from normality.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

The testing cases with missing results will be assigned the worst performance. Thus, there is no missing data for the results analysis. Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

The statistical analysis will be conducted using R or Python's SciPy and Pandas libraries, which are widely used in scientific research and provide robust tools for statistical evaluations.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We will verify the performance of the ensembles of top teams.

Cross-center variability and modality-specific failure mode will be evaluated.

TASK 2: Mitral Valve Segmentation from 3D Transesophageal Echocardiography

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Mitral valve (MV) disease is a prevalent cardiovascular condition and a leading indication for surgical and transcatheter intervention, particularly in elderly populations. Successful mitral valve repair relies heavily on accurate understanding of patient-specific valve anatomy, as the mitral valve exhibits complex geometry, large inter-patient variability, and diverse pathological manifestations. Three-dimensional transesophageal echocardiography (3D TEE) has become a key imaging modality for intraoperative assessment and procedural planning due to its real-time capability and high anatomical fidelity. However, manual segmentation of the mitral valve leaflets from 3D TEE volumes is labor-intensive, time-consuming, and subject to inter-observer variability, limiting its scalability and clinical utility.

From a technical perspective, automatic mitral valve segmentation from 3D TEE remains a challenging problem due to ultrasound-specific artifacts, signal dropout, thin leaflet structures, and ambiguous boundaries between leaflets and surrounding tissues. Although recent deep learning approaches have demonstrated promising accuracy, progress in this field has been hindered by the lack of publicly available, well-annotated benchmark datasets and standardized evaluation protocols.

This challenge aims to establish a unified benchmark for fully automatic mitral valve segmentation from 3D transesophageal echocardiography, providing curated datasets, clinically meaningful annotations, and consistent evaluation metrics. The envisioned impact of this challenge is to stimulate methodological innovation, enable fair comparison of algorithms, and accelerate the translation of robust AI-based mitral valve analysis tools into patient-specific modeling, intervention planning, and training workflows, ultimately supporting more precise and personalized mitral valve care.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Mitral Valve; Echocardiography; Segmentation; Foundational Model

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Organizers:

1. Tao Jia (Chongqing Normal University)
2. Mohammad Yaqub (Mohamed bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence)

3. Wei Hu (The University of Manchester)
4. Henggui Zhang (The University of Manchester)
5. Haibo Ni (Nanjing University)
6. Pan Zeng(Chongqing Normal University)
- 7.Wenfeng Zhang(Chongqing Normal University)
- 8.Yi Zhang(Chongqing Normal University)
- 9.Wen Yang(Chongqing Normal University)

Advisors:

1. Jieyun Bai (The Univeristy of Auckland)
2. Jichao Zhao (The University of Auckland)
3. Karim Lekadir (University of Barcelona)
4. Dong Ni (Shenzhen University)
5. Shuo Li (Case Western Reserve University)

Contributors:

1. Patrick Carnahan (Western University)
2. Qinyuan Zeng (The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University)
3. Jingyi He (The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University)
4. Yu Zhang (The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University)
5. Li Wang (Guangzhou Women and Children's Medical Center)
6. Yuxin Huang (Zhujiang Hospital of Southern Medical University)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Wei Hu (wei369.workstation@cqnu.edu.cn)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes, clinicians are an integral part of the organizing team and play a central role in ensuring the clinical relevance, annotation quality, and overall validity of the challenge. The clinical experts involved include Qinyuan Zeng, Jingyi He, and Yu Zhang (The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University), as well as Li Wang (Guangzhou Women and Children's Medical Center) and Yuxin Huang (Zhujiang Hospital of Southern Medical University). Their primary responsibilities include:

1. Providing real-world clinical data acquired under routine diagnostic conditions across multiple institutions and patient populations;
2. Performing and supervising expert annotations, including landmark identification and segmentation mask labeling, in accordance with standardized clinical protocols;
3. Evaluating annotation quality and inter-rater consistency to ensure that the reference labels accurately reflect true clinical variability and meet established diagnostic standards.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some

modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

The 1st MICCAI Workshop on Medical World Models in MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

<https://www.codabench.org/>

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

The official website is not yet publicly available at this stage. For reference, the previous IUGC 2025 was hosted on the CodaBench platform at: <https://www.codabench.org/competitions/7108/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Participants are required to use all unlabeled data to develop semi-supervised methods

We expect the solution to process one case within 10 seconds on a 12 GB GPU.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Participants were allowed to use only publicly available external datasets and publicly released pre-trained models.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

1. Certificates and cash awards for the top teams, the team with the most innovative method, and the teams with the careful method description.
2. The top 10 teams will be invited to give oral presentations at the MICCAI 2026 event and will be encouraged to submit extended versions of their methods to a related IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering (TBME) Special Issue.
3. Co-author of the challenge compendium paper, which will be submitted to a top journal (MedIA/TMI).

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The top 10 performing methods will be publicly announced by the organizers. The announcement will include the team names and overall ranking based on the official evaluation metrics defined for the challenge.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

1. Authorship Qualification: Members of top-10 teams who have made significant contributions to the conceptualization, design, execution, or interpretation of the research presented are qualified as authors.
2. Independent Publications: Participating teams are allowed to publish their results separately. However, this should be done in a manner that respects the collective efforts of the challenge.
3. Embargo Period: An embargo period allows the challenge organizers to publish a comprehensive challenge paper first. During this period, individual teams are encouraged to refrain from publishing their complete findings independently.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker container

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participating teams are allowed to validate their methods using the validation set provided by the organizers. Each submission will receive a validation score, which serves solely as a sanity check to verify that the submission is complete and correctly formatted. This validation score is not used for algorithm ranking, comparative

evaluation, or determination of final challenge results.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Training data release: 15/04/2026

Validation data release: 01/06/2026

Evaluation: 01/07/2026

Submission deadline: 01/08/2026

Winner and invitation speakers: 01/09/2026

Announcement of results at MICCAI 2026: (subject to change depending on the MICCAI 2026 deadlines)

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

We reannotate the open datasets in this challenge, hence no formal ethics review and IRB approval was required. Each institution contributing to the open datasets secured the approval of its institutional review board and institutional compliance Officers.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation software developed by the organizers will be publicly available to all participants. The code used for submission evaluation and ranking generation will be hosted in an open repository (e.g., GitHub), accompanied by comprehensive documentation, usage instructions, and platform requirements. A direct repository link will be provided on the challenge website, allowing participants to download, review, and locally run the evaluation pipeline to validate their submissions before final testing.

To facilitate fair comparison and help participants calibrate model development, an official baseline model will also be released. This will include a reference implementation, a pre-trained foundation-model checkpoint, and detailed instructions for fine-tuning and inference on the challenge dataset. Baseline performance scores will be provided as a transparent reference for benchmarking and result interpretation.

This open-access evaluation framework, together with the baseline-supported design, ensures transparency, reproducibility, and fairness throughout the challenge while enabling meaningful and consistent comparison across all participating methods.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Algorithm code release and corresponding conference paper submission will be prerequisites for award eligibility and further use of the data. To this end, GitHub repository URL containing the source code for their implemented method and conference paper following the guidelines will need to be provided.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The organizers declare no conflicts of interest.

During the challenge, only the organizers have access to the test dataset and its labels. Participating teams have no access to the test annotations. All test labels will be publicly released six months after the conclusion of the challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance

- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

CAD, Intervention follow up, Screening, Research, Surgery

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort is composed of patients with clinically significant mitral valve disease, undergoing diagnostic ultrasound investigation with a view to intervention.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort consists of mitral valve data acquired from adult patients with clinically significant mitral valve disease.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Echocardiography

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The provided data include the original echocardiography, and the corresponding mitral valve segmentation masks.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No patient information is shared except for the labels

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The image data are acquired from the cardiac region, with a specific focus on the mitral valve and its adjacent anatomical structures as visualized by echocardiography.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Mitral valve segmentation

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Complexity,Sensitivity,Specificity

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Philips Epiq cardiac ultrasound system

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Imaging was acquired according to clinical standard of care. Mid-esophageal (en-face) views are used to image the mitral valve using TEE probes. Images were then converted from Philips DICOM to cartesian format using Philips QLab.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

All images are acquired by clinical experts in clinical cardiac imaging and supervised by leaders in the field.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A "case" refers to the entire set of data associated with an individual patient.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The total number of cases is 200 divided as follow: 130 Training, 20 Validation, 50 Testing

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

All datasets provided in this challenge are fully annotated.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The total number of cases in this challenge is 200, divided into 130 training cases, 20 validation cases, and 50 test cases. This data split was designed to balance algorithm development, model tuning, and robust final evaluation. The training and validation sets are derived from datasets used in previous challenge editions, providing a stable and well-characterized foundation for method development, while the test set consists entirely of newly acquired

cases that were not available in earlier challenges. This strict separation ensures an unbiased assessment of generalization performance on unseen data. The relatively larger test set supports reliable performance comparison and ranking, while the training and validation sizes remain sufficient for training and hyperparameter optimization, with all splits maintaining representative distributions of mitral valve pathologies.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The data distributions in training, validation and test set are chosen according to real-world distribution.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

We have provided a total of more than 50 newly collected, unpublished ultrasound images for the challenge.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Annotations are completed via a semi-automated process, in which an existing automatic method is applied to generate a preliminary annotation, which is then manually jointly edited by 2 annotators until agreement is reached.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

- 1) Identifying clinical cases of patients with severe mitral regurgitation undergoing surgical intervention
- 2) Expert review of imaging quality with a view to segmentation
- 3) Evaluation and processing of image data using Philips QLab to generate cartesian volume compatible with 3D Slicer
- 4) Using 3D Slicer, apply automatic segmentation based on DeepMitral, followed by manual review and modification by both annotators
- 5) Tabulating segmented files by pathology

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Annotations completed jointly by a clinical expert and a data science expert.

- 1) Senior cardiology fellow undertaking a PhD in mitral valve disease under supervision of mitral imaging experts.
- 2) Senior PhD candidate with 4 years of experience working on mitral valve segmentation.

We employ a domain-specific manual annotation and quality-control pipeline involving nine professional annotators. For each anatomical or clinical domain, initial annotations are performed by a dedicated team consisting of an experienced sonographer and a trained annotator. All annotations are subsequently reviewed and adjudicated by senior clinical specialists.

To assess annotation reliability, inter-observer variability is evaluated on a randomly selected subset of 30 images,

independently annotated by three annotators. We report (i) annotation variability using evaluation metrics, and (ii) agreement at the measurement level, including intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC) and absolute error distributions of derived clinical parameters. This procedure ensures the reliability and clinical validity of the reference annotations used for evaluation.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

For this challenge, we do not merge multiple annotations, instead, all annotations are published to participants.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Data is pre-processed by converting the Philips DICOM files to cartesian format stored in Nifti format, with all meta-data stripped except for image size and spacing. Any further data processing is left up to the teams.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Mitral leaflet segmentations can be difficult due to large amount of variability between valves, as well as image quality and ultrasound signal dropout. Additionally, differentiation between leaflet and chordae tendineae can be difficult in some cases. These are known limitations of mitral valve imaging using using 3D TEE. Typical inter-user variability for mitral valve segmentations falls around 0.7mm, or 2-3 voxels.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Cases are reviewed and those with image quality deemed to be too poor to attempt segmentation were removed from the dataset, so only cases with sufficiently clear imaging are used to ensure the availability of high quality data.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), Hausdorff distance (HD), Average Surface Distance (ASD)

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) is used to quantify the spatial overlap between the predicted segmentation and the reference annotation, which is a standard and widely accepted metric for medical image segmentation. Accurate overlap is essential to ensure reliable delineation of the mitral valve anatomy.

Hausdorff Distance (HD) is included to evaluate boundary accuracy by measuring the maximum deviation between segmentation contours. This metric is particularly important for assessing clinically relevant boundary errors that may impact anatomical measurements and treatment planning.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

HD, Dice, and ASD scores are computed for each case in the test set.

For each metric, the mean performance across all cases is calculated to obtain the task-level metric score.

Rankings are then determined independently for each metric based on these mean scores. To ensure comparability across metrics with different scales and optimization directions, metric scores are normalized prior to aggregation.

The final task ranking is obtained by averaging the normalized per-metric rankings, providing a balanced assessment across complementary performance indicators. In the event of a tie, the submission with the lower HD score will be ranked higher due to its stronger boundary accuracy and clinical relevance.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For submissions with missing results on one or more test cases, the missing values will be penalized by assigning a score equivalent to the worst performance observed for the corresponding metric among all valid submissions. This strategy ensures fair comparison and discourages incomplete submissions while maintaining a consistent ranking framework.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The ranking scheme was designed to provide a fair, robust, and clinically meaningful evaluation by jointly considering complementary aspects of segmentation quality. Specifically, Dice and Hausdorff Distance (HD) scores are first computed on a per-case basis to capture case-level variability and avoid bias toward specific image characteristics, after which the mean value of each metric is calculated across all cases to summarize overall performance. Rankings are then determined independently for each metric to prevent scale differences from causing one metric to dominate the evaluation. The final ranking is obtained by averaging the per-metric rankings, thereby assigning equal importance to region overlap accuracy (Dice) and boundary precision (HD, ASD) and encouraging balanced algorithmic performance rather than metric-specific optimization. In the event of a tie, preference is given to the submission with the lower HD and ASD scores, as boundary errors are more sensitive to clinically relevant outliers and better reflect safety-critical segmentation inaccuracies.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

The statistical approaches applied in the challenge analysis are structured as follows:

1. **Missing Data Handling:** Multiple imputation techniques will be adopted to address missing data, ensuring the robustness and reliability of the analysis despite incomplete dataset information.
2. **Ranking Variability Assessment:** Statistical metrics including standard deviation and confidence intervals will be calculated for each algorithm's performance across different evaluation indices, to quantify performance variability. Additionally, non-parametric tests (e.g., the Wilcoxon signed-rank test) will be employed to conduct pairwise comparisons of algorithm performance.
3. **Data Assumption Validation:** Prior to implementing any statistical methods, pre-validation tests will be performed on the dataset. This includes the Shapiro-Wilk test for assessing data normality and Levene's test for evaluating variance homogeneity, ensuring the dataset meets the prerequisite assumptions of the selected statistical approaches.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Performance estimate precision is evaluated using percentile bootstrap confidence intervals on the test set (95% CI, 1,000 resamples).

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across test cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Performance variability across test cases is evaluated using per-case metric distributions, reported via SD and IQR, supplemented with boxplots/violin plots and explicit outlier reporting.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap. The Bootstrap is a simple nonparametric method that relies on minimal assumptions.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Statistical significance of performance differences between algorithms is assessed using pairwise non-parametric hypothesis testing on per-case performance metrics computed on the test set. Specifically, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test is employed for paired comparisons, as all algorithms are evaluated on the same test cases and metric distributions may deviate from normality.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

The testing cases with missing results will be assigned the worst performance. Thus, there is no missing data for the results analysis. Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

The statistical analysis will be conducted using R or Python's SciPy and Pandas libraries, which are widely used in scientific research and provide robust tools for statistical evaluations.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,

- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Further analysis for the purpose of the challenge summary paper will include an evaluation of the performance of an ensemble predictor combining the top performing submissions compared to each individual submission. We will investigate the variability of predictions across different algorithms, and identify common problems, or specific cases where performance was worse, with the aim of identifying the underlying cause of these problems. This could be related to image quality, or a unique valve pathology that provides a more difficult case for an automated segmentation approach.

Cross-center variability and modality-specific failure mode will be evaluated.

TASK 3: Mitral Valve Detection from Surgical Video

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Mitral valve (MV) disease is a major cause of morbidity worldwide, and successful surgical repair or replacement critically depends on accurate intraoperative understanding of valve anatomy, leaflet motion, and spatial relationships. Surgical videos, routinely acquired during open and minimally invasive cardiac procedures, provide rich, real-time visual information that directly reflects the surgeon's view and decision-making context. However, extracting clinically meaningful information from these videos remains highly challenging due to complex valve dynamics, specular reflections, blood occlusion, motion blur, viewpoint variability, and the absence of standardized annotations. From a biomedical perspective, reliable detection of the mitral valve and its key anatomical components in surgical video can support objective assessment of valve exposure, procedural guidance, quality control, and surgical skill analysis. From a technical perspective, this task poses demanding computer vision problems, requiring robust methods capable of handling non-rigid motion, fine-grained structures, appearance variability, and limited labeled data. This challenge aims to establish the first standardized benchmark for mitral valve detection from surgical video, providing curated datasets, expert annotations, and unified evaluation protocols to foster the development and fair comparison of automated methods. The envisioned impact is to accelerate progress in video-based cardiac surgical intelligence, bridge the gap between algorithmic advances and intraoperative clinical needs, and ultimately support safer, more precise, and more reproducible mitral valve interventions through data-driven technologies.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Mitral Valve; Surgical Video; Detection; Foundational Model

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Organizers:

1. Jieyun Bai (The University of Auckland)
2. Xiaoshen Zhang (The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University)
3. Yufei Zhan (The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University)
4. Yitong Tang (Jinan University)

Advisors:

1. Jichao Zhao (The University of Auckland)
2. Karim Lekadir (University of Barcelona)

3. Jun Ma (University of Toronto)
4. Kuanquan Wang (Harbin Institute of Technology)
5. Shuo Li (Case Western Reserve University)

Contributors:

1. Bo Deng (Jinan University)
2. Jiake Li (Jinan University)
3. Hua Lu (The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University)
4. Qinyuan Zeng (The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University)
5. Jingyi He (The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University)
6. Yu Zhang (The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Jieyun Bai (jbai996@aucklanduni.ac.nz)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes, clinicians are an integral part of the organizing team and play a central role in ensuring the clinical relevance, annotation quality, and overall validity of the challenge. The clinical experts involved include Xiaoshen Zhang, Hua Lu, Yufei Zhan, Qinyuan Zeng, Jingyi He, and Yu Zhang (The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University). Their primary responsibilities include:

1. Providing real-world clinical data acquired under routine diagnostic conditions across multiple institutions and patient populations;
2. Performing and supervising expert annotations, in accordance with standardized clinical protocols;
3. Evaluating annotation quality and inter-rater consistency to ensure that the reference labels accurately reflect true clinical variability and meet established diagnostic standards.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

The 1st MICCAI Workshop on Medical World Models in MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

<https://www.codabench.org/>

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

The official website is not yet publicly available at this stage. For reference, the previous IUGC 2025 was hosted on the CodaBench platform at: <https://www.codabench.org/competitions/7108/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Participants are required to use all unlabeled data to develop semi-supervised methods

We expect the solution to process one case within 10 seconds on a 12 GB GPU.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Participants were allowed to use only publicly available external datasets and publicly released pre-trained models.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

1. Certificates and cash awards for the top teams, the team with the most innovative method, and the teams with the careful method description.

2. The top 10 teams will be invited to give oral presentations at the MICCAI 2026 event and will be encouraged to submit extended versions of their methods to a related IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering (TBME) Special Issue.

3. Co-author of the challenge compendium paper, which will be submitted to a top journal (MedIA/TMI).

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The top 10 performing methods will be publicly announced by the organizers. The announcement will include the team names and overall ranking based on the official evaluation metrics defined for the challenge.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

1. Authorship Qualification: Members of top-10 teams who have made significant contributions to the conceptualization, design, execution, or interpretation of the research presented are qualified as authors.

2. Independent Publications: Participating teams are allowed to publish their results separately. However, this should be done in a manner that respects the collective efforts of the challenge.

3. Embargo Period: An embargo period allows the challenge organizers to publish a comprehensive challenge paper first. During this period, individual teams are encouraged to refrain from publishing their complete findings independently.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker container

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participating teams are allowed to validate their methods using the validation set provided by the organizers. Each submission will receive a validation score, which serves solely as a sanity check to verify that the submission is complete and correctly formatted. This validation score is not used for algorithm ranking, comparative evaluation, or determination of final challenge results.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Training data release: 15/04/2026

Validation data release: 01/06/2026

Evaluation: 01/07/2026

Submission deadline: 01/08/2026

Winner and invitation speakers: 01/09/2026

Announcement of results at MICCAI 2026: (subject to change depending on the MICCAI 2026 deadlines)

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The data are used as retrospective analysis from hospital, ethics approval is not necessary for the data.

Permission has been granted by the appropriate review boards to release anonymous image data publicly.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation software developed by the organizers will be publicly available to all participants. The code used for submission evaluation and ranking generation will be hosted in an open repository (e.g., GitHub), accompanied by comprehensive documentation, usage instructions, and platform requirements. A direct repository link will be provided on the challenge website, allowing participants to download, review, and locally run the evaluation pipeline to validate their submissions before final testing.

To facilitate fair comparison and help participants calibrate model development, an official baseline model will also be released. This will include a reference implementation, a pre-trained foundation-model checkpoint, and

detailed instructions for fine-tuning and inference on the challenge dataset. Baseline performance scores will be provided as a transparent reference for benchmarking and result interpretation.

This open-access evaluation framework, together with the baseline-supported design, ensures transparency, reproducibility, and fairness throughout the challenge while enabling meaningful and consistent comparison across all participating methods.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Algorithm code release and corresponding conference paper submission will be prerequisites for award eligibility and further use of the data. To this end, GitHub repository URL containing the source code for their implemented method and conference paper following the guidelines will need to be provided.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The organizers declare no conflicts of interest.

During the challenge, only the organizers have access to the test dataset and its labels. Participating teams have no access to the test annotations. All test labels will be publicly released six months after the conclusion of the challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

CAD, Assistance, Education, Intervention planning, Surgery, Training, Treatment planning

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Detection

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort consists of adult patients with severe mitral valve stenosis or regurgitation.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort comprises surgical videos acquired from adult patients diagnosed with clinically significant mitral valve disease undergoing mitral valve interventions.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Single channel of endoscopic video

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The provided data include the surgical videos and bounding box labels

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No patient information is shared except for the labels.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The image data are acquired from the cardiac region, with a specific focus on the mitral valve and its adjacent anatomical structures as visualized by surgical videos. Note: In this challenge, 40 cases have paired CT and surgical video data.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Mitral valve detection

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Complexity,Sensitivity,Specificity

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The Data Recorder

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The videos will be captured at 720p and 30fps

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The First Affiliated Hospital of Jinan University

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

All images are acquired by clinical experts and supervised by leaders in the field.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A "case" refers to a surgical video associated with an individual patient.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The total number of cases is 100 divided as follow: 40 Training, 15 Validation, 45 Testing

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

All datasets provided in this challenge are fully annotated.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The total number of cases in this challenge is 100, divided into 40 training cases, 15 validation cases, and 45 test cases. This data split was intentionally designed to balance effective algorithm development, model tuning, and rigorous final evaluation under realistic data availability constraints. The training set provides sufficient examples for learning robust representations, while the validation set supports reliable hyperparameter optimization and model selection without overfitting. A relatively larger test set was allocated to enable statistically reliable performance comparison and ranking, ensuring that final results reflect generalization to unseen surgical video cases. All data splits include representative variations in mitral valve anatomy, pathology, and surgical viewpoints, thereby supporting fair evaluation and clinically meaningful assessment of algorithm robustness.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The training, validation, and test sets were constructed to reflect realistic clinical distributions of mitral valve anatomy, pathology severity, and surgical viewpoints rather than enforcing an artificial class balance. This choice was made to ensure that the challenge data closely resemble real-world intraoperative scenarios, thereby promoting the development of robust methods that generalize well to routine clinical practice. All splits include representative variations in patient characteristics, disease presentations, and video acquisition conditions, supporting fair evaluation while avoiding bias toward rare or overrepresented cases.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All cases in this challenge are newly acquired surgical videos and have not been previously published or released. The dataset consists of 100 cases, with 100% of the data being unseen and unpublished, ensuring a fair evaluation of generalization performance.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The reference annotations for this challenge were generated through manual annotation of the surgical videos. A total of seven human annotators were involved, including three experienced cardiac surgeons and four clinically trained medical students. The annotation process followed a standardized protocol defined by the challenge organizers to ensure consistency across training, validation, and test sets. All annotations were reviewed for quality and anatomical correctness, with expert surgeons providing guidance and final verification where necessary, ensuring that the reference annotations accurately represent clinically meaningful mitral valve structures.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The crowd-sourced annotators were already trained and experienced in spatial annotation for surgical tools. Each frame will be annotated then reviewed by the annotation team to ensure quality.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Annotators will have significant experience in labelling bounding boxes for surgical tools and surgical steps. We employ a domain-specific manual annotation and quality-control pipeline involving nine professional annotators. For each anatomical or clinical domain, initial annotations are performed by a dedicated team consisting of an experienced sonographer and a trained annotator. All annotations are subsequently reviewed and adjudicated by senior clinical specialists.

To assess annotation reliability, inter-observer variability is evaluated on a randomly selected subset of 30 images, independently annotated by three annotators. We report (i) annotation variability using evaluation metrics, and (ii) agreement at the measurement level, including intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC) and absolute error distributions of derived clinical parameters. This procedure ensures the reliability and clinical validity of the reference annotations used for evaluation.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

For this challenge, we do not merge multiple annotations, instead, all annotations are published to participants.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Raw video frames will not be altered.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter- and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

The main sources of annotation-related error include:

1. Inter-annotator variability: Differences in how annotators identify and delineate mitral valve structures, particularly in complex cases with subtle boundaries or low contrast. This variability may lead to differences in boundary placement and shape, typically within a small spatial range around the valve contours.
2. Intra-annotator variability: Variations in annotations produced by the same expert across different cases or at different times, arising from subjective interpretation or image quality differences. Such inconsistencies mainly affect fine-scale boundary details.
3. Annotation ambiguity: In some cases, the boundaries of the mitral valve are inherently ambiguous due to imaging limitations or pathological alterations, which can result in uncertain or partially overlapping annotations.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

There is a possibility of a dropped event that can cause error in the training tool presence labels. However, we do not expect this to happen frequently. The step labels would not have any other relevant source of error.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Mean average precision (mAP) for different intersection over union (IoU) values 0.50:0.05:0.95 will be used to assess performance of tool bounding box prediction algorithms. The proposed method must achieve a processing speed of 30 fps, with only the mitral valve bounding box being detected.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

This is the standard metric used for bounding box prediction algorithms. By varying the thresholds, this metric provides a more thorough evaluation of tool localization/keypoint detection accuracy. The surgical step category is a standard classification problem where average f1-score can accurately measure the performance of the models. This metric has proven to be a good measure of model performances in our previous challenges as well.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are

aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

The performance ranking for Task 3 will be determined based on the evaluation metric results, specifically the mean average precision (mAP) computed across IoU thresholds from 0.50 to 0.95 for mitral valve bounding box detection. Submissions will be ranked according to their mAP scores, with higher mAP values corresponding to higher rankings. To ensure consistency with the overall multi-task evaluation framework, metric scores will be normalized before aggregation with other tasks, enabling fair comparison and balanced integration into the final overall ranking.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For submissions with missing results on one or more test cases, the missing values will be penalized by assigning a score equivalent to the worst performance observed for the corresponding metric among all valid submissions. This strategy ensures fair comparison and discourages incomplete submissions while maintaining a consistent ranking framework.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Using the standard metrics being used within the object detection research seems like the right way to rank teams. The spatial detection metric tests the algorithms for detection of objects of different sizes which will be useful in differentiating high and low performing teams. Similarly, mean f1-score will reward and penalize the predictions for correct/incorrect predictions accordingly.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

The statistical approaches applied in the challenge analysis are structured as follows:

1. **Missing Data Handling:** Multiple imputation techniques will be adopted to address missing data, ensuring the robustness and reliability of the analysis despite incomplete dataset information.
2. **Ranking Variability Assessment:** Statistical metrics including standard deviation and confidence intervals will be calculated for each algorithm's performance across different evaluation indices, to quantify performance variability. Additionally, non-parametric tests (e.g., the Wilcoxon signed-rank test) will be employed to conduct pairwise comparisons of algorithm performance.
3. **Data Assumption Validation:** Prior to implementing any statistical methods, pre-validation tests will be performed on the dataset. This includes the Shapiro-Wilk test for assessing data normality and Levene's test for evaluating variance homogeneity, ensuring the dataset meets the prerequisite assumptions of the selected statistical approaches.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Performance estimate precision is evaluated using percentile bootstrap confidence intervals on the test set (95% CI, 1,000 resamples).

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Performance variability across test cases is evaluated using per-case metric distributions, reported via SD and IQR, supplemented with boxplots/violin plots and explicit outlier reporting.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap. The Bootstrap is a simple nonparametric method that relies on minimal assumptions.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Statistical significance of performance differences between algorithms is assessed using pairwise non-parametric hypothesis testing on per-case performance metrics computed on the test set. Specifically, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test is employed for paired comparisons, as all algorithms are evaluated on the same test cases and metric distributions may deviate from normality.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

The testing cases with missing results will be assigned the worst performance. Thus, there is no missing data for the results analysis. Ranking variability will be characterized using the bootstrap.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

The statistical analysis will be conducted using R or Python's SciPy and Pandas libraries, which are widely used in scientific research and provide robust tools for statistical evaluations.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Additional analysis will be performed on the results to check for ranking variability.

Cross-center variability and modality-specific failure mode will be evaluated.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

[1] Zeng A, Wu C, Lin G, et al. ImageCAS: A large-scale dataset and benchmark for coronary artery segmentation based on computed tomography angiography images[J]. Computerized Medical Imaging and Graphics, 2023, 109: 102287.

[2] Bai, J., Khobo, I., Lu, Y., Ni, D., Yaqub, M., Lekadir, K., Ma, J., & Li, S. (2025). Landmark Detection Challenge for Intrapartum Ultrasound Measurement Meeting the Actual Clinical Assessment of Labor Progress. Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention 2025 (MICCAI). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15172238>

- [3] Zia, A., Berniker, M., Perreault, C., Nespolo, R., & Jarc, A. (2024). Surgical Visual Understanding Challenge (SurgVU). International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention 2025 (MICCAI). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14054184>
- [4] Chen Z, Bai J, Li S, et al. CFVP-Net: Coarse-to-Fine Visual Perception Network for Aortic Dissection Segmentation[C]//2025 IEEE International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedicine (BIBM). IEEE, 2025: 5809-5816.
- [5]Zhu J, Bai J, Zhou Z, et al. RAS dataset: a 3D cardiac LGE-MRI dataset for segmentation of right atrial cavity[J]. Scientific Data, 2024, 11(1): 401.
- [6]Bai, Jieyun, et al. "A benchmark framework for the right atrium cavity segmentation from lge-mris." IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging (2025).

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

This challenge is part of The 1st MICCAI Workshop on Medical World Models in MICCAI 2026. Additionally, outstanding and high-impact contributions will be invited to submit extended manuscripts to the IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering (TBME) Special Issue entitled "Digital Twins, Simulation-Based AI and Medical World Models." This pathway provides an opportunity for selected teams to present deeper methodological insights, extended validation, and translational perspectives beyond the scope of proceedings papers.